

THEME: AGRICULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN PROBLEMS IN PRODUCING PRODUCTS

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Abstract: the article describes the results of agricultural reforms in our country, achievements in the cultivation of agricultural and livestock products, the organization of clusters, problems in the production of agricultural products and their solutions

Key words: agricultural reforms, farming, agrocluster, fruits and vegetables, intensive method, livestock products, fodder, peasant and family farms, breeding, meat, milk, livestock complexes.

Agriculture is a priority sector of the economy. Because farming and animal husbandry, which are the main branches of agriculture, produce the necessary food products for the population. The products grown in these sectors are used as the main raw materials in the production of consumer goods in the food and light industry sectors of the industry. Production in agriculture is somewhat difficult, and its volume is affected not only by human factors, but also by natural factors. A very cold winter leads to the drying up of cold-resistant fruit trees (pomegranates, persimmons, figs, etc.), a lack of crops (wheat, barley, sesame, peas, etc.) planted due to the lack of timely rains, and a hot summer leads to a decrease in productivity.

Despite such vagaries of nature, the country's agriculture has been achieving good results year after year.

In accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev dated November 23, 2021 "On measures to develop family entrepreneurship in fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture and increase the share of farmers in agricultural production", 200 thousand hectares of low-yielding land reduced from cotton and grain have been reserved and if possible, it is decided to lease for 10 years to the people who will establish farms, and to plant vegetables, oil and oil crops (such as flax, sesame, sunflower) on these lands. As a result of this, a certain part of the village population will be provided with a job and will earn income by selling the grown products. At the same time, the supply of products to the population will be improved, price stability will be ensured, and the surplus will be directed to export. As a result of agro-reforms and measures, the volume of agricultural products grown in our country is increasing year by year. 28918.3 billion in our country in 2015. 123858.8 billion soums were produced by all farms in 2020. soums, and in 2021 152,130.4 billion. Soum worth of products were grown, that is, more than 5.3 times. Changes in purchase prices of agricultural products also had an impact to some extent. For example, according to the Presidential Decree of May 28, 2022 "On additional measures to introduce the market principle in grain production and sale", the price of 1 ton of wheat will be from 1 million 500 thousand soums, starting from June 1, 2022, 1 ton of wheat will be from 3 million soums based on market prices (increased by 2 times) reception is set. As a result,

wheat-growing farms, if they suffered a loss without covering their expenses, started to earn because they were given the right to freely sell at market prices.

The results of the increase of agricultural products in the following years are clearly expressed by their indicators in kind. Therefore, we consider the production volumes of the main agricultural products.

Production of agricultural products in Uzbekistan in 2011-2022¹

Table 1

No	Indicators (thousand tons.)	Years				
		2011	2015	2020	2022	2022 in % compared to 2010
1	Don	7504.3	8173.5	7636.0	7634.6	101.7
	Including: Wheat	6745.0	6964.7	6157.8	5984.8	88.7
2	Cotton raw material	3442.8	3361.3	3064.0	3372.9	97.9
3	Potatoes	1694.8	2696.9	3143.8	3285.6	193.8
4	Vegetables	6346.5	10129.3	10431.4	10850.2	171.0
5	Food policy	1182.4	1853.6	2134.4	2285.3	193.2
6	Fruits and berries	1710.3	2746.1	2812.6	2852.6	166.8
		987.3	1579.3	1606.9	1695.3	174.0

As can be seen from the table, the production of all agricultural products except for grain and cotton raw materials has increased by 2022 at a very high rate compared to 2011. The reason for this is the zoning of low-yielding cotton and grain lands for planting fruits and vegetables, as well as the results of the work done to raise (increase) their productivity. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev dated December 15, 2021 "On measures to support the fruit and vegetable industry by the state, to further develop the cluster and cooperation system in the network" established the establishment of clusters engaged in the cultivation, storage and processing of fruits and vegetables. Fruit and vegetable clusters provide contract assistance to farmers for quality, high-yielding, pest-resistant seeds, required fertilizers, machinery and similar services. The farmer buys the crops grown on farms under the contract, processes them, and supplies the population with fruits and vegetables based on the principle of "from the field to the farm (to the market)".

As a result of the measures taken by the President of the Republic and the Government for the development of agriculture in our country, production in this field is increasing year by year. The total volume of agricultural products in 2022 is 347.6 trillion soums, which is 185.5% more than the volume of products grown in 2018 (2018-187.4 trillion soums were grown),

¹ The table was compiled by the author based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

that is, almost 2 times more. In this regard, great attention was paid to providing the population with quality meat and dairy products. The total livestock products increased from 89019.2 billion soums in 2018 to 151285.1 billion soums in 2021, i.e. by 170.0%. The President of the country Sh. Mirziyoyev's January 29, 2020 "On additional measures of state support for the livestock industry" was of great importance in increasing livestock production. This decision envisages improving cattle breeds, increasing livestock feed, and allocating subsidies to livestock farmers from the state budget.

Table 1

Livestock production in Uzbekistan in 2018-2022 (thousand tons)

No	Years	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2022 vs. 2018 %
	show-little ones						
1	Meat (live weight)	2430.5	2473.6	2519.6	2635.1	2726.0	112.2
2	Milk	10466.4	10714.3	10976.9	11274.2	11629.4	111.2
3	Eggs (million pieces)	7459.3	7771.2	7781.2	7788.4	8129.3	109.0
4	Wool	34.6	35.1	35.4	36.3	37.3	107.8
5	Black leather (thousands)	1085.2	1150.7	1152.1	1252.4	1302.3	120.0
6	Fish	17.9	21.4	20.9	22.8	23.5	131.3

As can be seen from the data in the table, there was an increase in all types of livestock products in these years. The main livestock products grew mainly by more than 10 percent over the 5-year period (2018-2022). Fish production increased from 17.9 thousand tons (2018) to 23.5 thousand tons (2022), that is, by 131.3 percent. This is the result of ongoing efforts to provide the population with nutritious, easily digestible, vitamin-rich fish products.

It should also be noted that, according to statistical data, the main, largest part of livestock products is grown in farmers and family farms. In 2022, 87.9% of the meat (in live weight), 93.4% of milk, 62.0% of eggs, 83.3% of wool, and 80.4% of obtained cattle hides belonged to farmers and family farms. Therefore, these farmers and households need expert help in growing livestock products, creating productive breeds of livestock, growing fodder, providing veterinary services, purchasing their products, and other activities. For this, the "Agrokizmat" organization is being formed, which unites local experts. Family cooperatives are being established in order to purchase livestock products produced by farmers and family farms and organize their processing.

When we analyze the production of livestock products by regions, the largest amount was produced by the regions of Samarkand (2022 - 19112.0 billion soums), Kashkadarya (2022 - 19099.4 billion soums) and Tashkent (2022 - 16623.9 billion soums). On the contrary, the least amount of livestock products was produced by the regions of Syrdarya (2022 - 4646.5 billion soums), Navoi (2022 - 9847.2 billion soums) and the Republic of Karakalpakstan (2022 - 6757.2 billion soums). In the regions where livestock products are grown in large quantities,

the territories are large, the population is large, and the conditions are there. The territory of Syrdarya region is flat, relatively small and adapted to agriculture. The territories of Navoi region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan are very large, and it will be necessary to find ways to increase the number of livestock and increase the volume of products.

Conclusions and suggestions. Along with the progress achieved in the cultivation of agricultural products, there are also shortcomings and problems in this field. These problems include:

- lack of knowledge and experience of farmers and farm managers in growing products and selling them;
- that the reclamation condition of irrigated lands is not of good quality;
- timely or incomplete fulfillment of contract terms with farms and clusters.

Based on the above, it is appropriate to implement the following recommendations:

- improvement of contractual relations between the enterprises that grow and process agricultural products on product delivery and acceptance;
- wide use of digital technologies is necessary for information exchange;
- prevention of the increase of debtor and creditor debts between the enterprises that grow agricultural products and their processing, timely implementation of calculations, formation of an effective system of financing production in this field;
- placement of high-yielding, disease- and pest-resistant, new and promising varieties of agricultural crops whose product quality meets market requirements.

Elimination of these shortcomings will serve to increase agricultural products and make farmers more profitable. Agricultural products grown in our Serkuyosh region, especially fruits and vegetables, melons, watermelons are sweet, rich in vitamins and trace elements necessary for human health. Therefore, these products meet the needs of the population and are exported to foreign countries.

The production of agricultural products in our country is increasing year by year. However, in order to continuously provide the growing population with a sufficient amount of agricultural products, to ensure food security, the following should be implemented:

- it will be necessary to increase feed and fodder for livestock. For this, it is necessary to increase the area of crops such as alfalfa and corn, and increase their productivity. Crop rotation will need to be strictly followed;
- taking into account the drought and water shortage, it is necessary to systematically breed drought-resistant perennial plants. This is especially effective in the foothills, steppes and desert zones;
- it is necessary to improve the composition of livestock products. Especially in meat production, it is necessary to increase the number of healthy rabbit and poultry meats, and fish, and to promote the fact that such meats are medicinal;
- further increase of livestock complexes in the field of dairy farming and dairy farming. It is necessary to determine ways to increase livestock fodder, reduce their cost, sales price;
- it will be necessary to provide farmers and family farms with productive, thoroughbred livestock, purchase livestock products, provide fodder, provide veterinary services, transport and process products according to sanitary and hygienic requirements.

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